

Catalytic effect of pre-micellar aggregates on oxidative degradation of acridine orange by acidic chlorite

Brijesh Pare^{a*}, Rajani Vijay^b, V. W. Bhagwat^b and Charles Fogliani^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Madhav Science College, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : brijesh_pare@hotmail.com

^bSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : rv1976@rediffmail.com

^cCharles Sturt University, Bathurst, New South Wales, Australia

Manuscript received 14 June 2006, revised 13 February 2007, accepted 27 February 2007

Abstract : Study of catalytic effect of pre-micellar aggregates on oxidative degradation of acridine orange by acidic chlorite has been investigated. With excess of other reactants, both un-catalyzed and catalyzed reactions follow pseudo-first order kinetics with respect to [AO⁺]. The un-catalyzed reaction follows fractional order kinetics in oxidant. Role of acid has been found to be complex. Increase in ionic strength by the addition of Na₂SO₄ resulted in decrease in rate constant value, suggesting involvement of oppositely charged species in the rate determining step. The overall stoichiometry of the reaction has been found to be

P=7-dimethylaminoquinoline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid. The lowest catalytic concentration for C₁₆TAB is found to be 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ which is much less than its CMC. The pre-micellar catalytic kinetic data has been rationalized in the light of various prominent models like Menger-Porteny's, Piskiewicz's and Raghavan-Shrinivasan's to understand the catalyzed mechanistic aspect of surfactant catalysis. The positive cooperative index ($n = 1.15$) has also been computed. On the basis of observed results and product characterization most plausible mechanisms for un-catalyzed and catalyzed reactions have been envisaged.

Keywords : Surfactant catalysis, acridine orange.

Textile industry is one of the water-intensive industry that consume large quantities of water for various processes and discharges equally large volumes of waste water containing a variety of pollutants. Textile wastes are colored and contain auxiliary chemicals like detergents etc. Dyes have long residence time in water and are hazardous in aquatic system^{1,2}. Thus, the color removal process and the degradation dynamics of the dye are of urgent need. Surfactants despite being a pollutant itself are important in theoretical and experimental fields due to their catalytic effects and their behavior as analogous to biological membranes³.

Surfactants are catalytically active even prior to their critical micellar concentration (CMC). A thorough scan of the literature reveals no information regarding study on the acridine class dyes. The oxidative degradation of

acridine orange by chlorite is basically a slow reaction but is effectively catalyzed by cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (C₁₆TAB). This prompted us to investigate the C₁₆TAB-catalyzed discoloration dynamics in detail.

The detailed kinetics of the un-catalyzed acridine orange-chlorite reaction along with the catalytic aspects of C₁₆TAB catalyzed reaction discussed in the light of various prominent models applicable to the surfactant catalysis.

The chemicals used were of analaR grade (Aldrich, B.D.H.) and the double distilled water was used throughout to prepare the solutions.

Materials :

The M/1000 aqueous solution acridine orange (Sigma) was prepared by dissolving 0.0369 g of AO⁺ in 100 ml double distilled water. Working solution was prepared

by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. Stock solution of sulphuric acid was prepared by diluting the calculated volume (from specific gravity) of acid with double distilled water and finally its concentration was determined by titrating it against standard NaOH solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. In order to avoid any error due to decomposition of the solution, an aqueous solution of sodium chlorite (Aldrich) was prepared daily. Working solution was prepared by dissolving 0.28 g of sodium chlorite in 25 ml of water for M/10 solution. The stock solution of the C₁₆TAB was prepared by dissolving 0.0364 g of C₁₆TAB in 50% acetic acid.

Experimental

The experimental conditions used were [AO⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [NaClO₂] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [C₁₆TAB] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, temp. = 298 K. The course of reaction was monitored at 490 nm and at known intervals time. The possibility of complexation of C₁₆TAB with dye was checked by direct complexation and scanning. Hyperchromic shift in the absorbance of dye from 0.689 to 0.709 on addition of 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ C₁₆TAB is the evidence of complexation of surfactant with dye.

Product analysis and stoichiometry :

For product analysis 300 mg of dye, 100 ml (0.1 mol dm⁻³) H₂SO₄ and 2 g of NaClO₂ were mixed and made up to 1000 ml by using deionised water. After complete decolourization the organic components were extracted with ether. Preliminary studies were carried out by TLC using benzene and ethyl acetate mixture (8 : 2) as an eluent. Chromatographic separation followed by IR spectrometric studies was done. The IR spectra of the sample showed strong absorption band at 1638 cm⁻¹ may be due to C=O stretching of carbonyl group. The lowering in the position of absorption band could be due to larger conjugation. Presence of carbonyl group is further substantiated by the presence of C-O stretching bands at 1151, 1014 and 971 cm⁻¹. The broad and strong bands at 3552 and 3416 cm⁻¹ show the presence of hydroxyl group. Generally the O-H stretching band of the carboxylic group gets superimposed upon C-H stretching at 3238 cm⁻¹ of benzene nucleus. Absorption bands at 1373, 1332 and 1151 cm⁻¹ supports the C-N stretching. Absence of N-H stretching pattern supports that dealkylation has not taken place. The intense absorption peak in between 1300-1200 cm⁻¹ for N-O stretching is absent. Thus, oxidation at the nitrogen atom and formation of N-oxide in the heterocyclic ring is unlikely. The absorption band at 1373 cm⁻¹ may be due to C-H bending vibration of -CH₃ groups. Based

on the IR spectra major product was identified as quinoline dicarboxylic acid (7-dimethylaminoquinoline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid). Literature reports that oxidation of acridine by various oxidants such as calcium hypochlorite in the presence of cobalt, bromine, sodium methoxide, potassium permanganate and ozone yields quinoline 2,3-dicarboxylic acid as a major product⁴. The similar product have been reported in the case of C₁₆TAB catalyzed oxidation of Methylene Violet⁵ by chloramine-T and acridine orange by chlorite⁶.

Stoichiometry was determined using varying ratios of the oxidant to AO⁺ for 24 h incubation. The absorbance at 490 nm was measured and residual ClO₂⁻ was determined iodometrically. Acridine orange and chlorite react in stoichiometry as follows :

P = 7-dimethylaminoquinoline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid.

Results and discussion

In a typical kinetic run, with [AO⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [ClO₂⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, a plot of log Absorbance versus time was linear indicating that reaction under chosen conditions follows pseudo-first order kinetics and order in [AO⁺] is unity. The mean pseudo-first order rate constant was found to be 4.45 × 10⁻⁴ ± 0.2 s⁻¹.

The rate of reaction increases with initial concentration of chlorite and H⁺ ions. The plot of log Absorbance vs log [oxidant] is linear with slopes 0.49 (R² = 0.99). Slope value suggests that the reaction had fractional order dependence on oxidant. The role of acid has been found to be complex.

With the reactants concentration AO⁺ = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, ClO₂⁻ = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, the initial ionic strength was found to be 0.009. An increase in ionic strength from 0.009 to 0.030 by the addition of neutral Na₂SO₄ resulted in the decrease in rate constant values from 3.0 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ to 1.66 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹. The plot of √μ vs log k' was linear with slope -1.19 (R² = 0.98), thus suggesting the participation of two oppositely charged species in rate determination step.

Stability of sodium chlorite solution is highly influenced by the change in pH. Reaction was studied in the pH range of 3.38 to 6.4. Change in pH was accomplished by addition of NaOH. The rate of reaction increases as the pH shifts towards the acidic side and slows down when it shifts towards the basic side. Optimum pH range was

found to be 3.7 to 4.1. In high acidic conditions (pH = 1 to 2.5) the reaction rate was found to retard owing to fast decomposition of oxidant and in basic conditions the reason for slow reaction was attributed to the fact that alkaline solutions of chlorite are quite stable.

The observed reaction orders with respect to [AO⁺] and [chlorite] is unity and fractional respectively, while the role of acid is complex. The negative salt effect suggests that the rate-determining step is the reaction between two oppositely charged species. Further, the plot of 1/*k* versus 1/[oxidant] is linear with non-zero intercept, which is an evidence of the formation of an intermediate complex. Thus, a tentative reaction mechanism is proposed as shown in Scheme 1.

The organic intermediate (I) is further oxidised in steps involving various chloro and oxychloro species to give the final reaction products. On the basis of well studied chemistry of acidic chlorite reactions, the following reactions need to be considered⁷⁻¹⁰.

Rationalization of pre-micellar catalysis :

All the characteristic properties of a surfactant originate from the fact that a hydrophobic group is forced to dissolve in water by hydrophilic group that is attached to the same molecule. The driving force for aggregation is the tendency of the hydrophobic part of the surfactant to aggregate because of mutual dislike of the solvent. When surfactants are added to water, they remain dispersed into separate molecules at low concentration. At a particular concentration, the surfactant molecules begin to associate to form aggregates or micelles. The addition of electrolyte and non-electrolyte impurities affects the CMC of surfactants. So, to understand the catalytic and mechanistic aspects of surfactant catalysis various prevalent models have been applied and the results are discussed in their light.

Menger and Portnoy's model :

Model advanced to explain the catalysis in presence of micelle are those due to Menger and Portnoy's¹¹ as well as Berezin¹². The variation of the rate constant with surfactant is generally treated on the assumptions that

Scheme 1

Table 1. Variation in C₁₆TAB concentration

[AO⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [ClO₂⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
[H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, temp. = 298 ± 0.1 K

[C ₁₆ TAB] × 10 ⁴ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³)	k''' × 10 ⁴ (s)
-	3.00
0.1	3.07
0.5	5.78
0.7	6.43
0.9	7.20
1.0	7.70
3.0	7.78
5.0	11.47

Mean of duplicate experiments.

substrate 'S' is distributed between the aqueous and micelle pseudo phase as given below :

This model leads to the relationship for micelle catalysis

$$\frac{1}{(k_\psi - k_w)} = \frac{1}{(k_m - k_w)} + \frac{1}{K_s (k_m - k_w)} \{ [D] - \text{CMC} \}$$

where, k_w , k_m and k_ψ are rate constants in aqueous phase, micelle medium and observed rate constant, respectively.

The linearity of plot between $1/(k_\psi - k_w)$ and $1/[D]$ suggests the applicability of the model and the formation of micelle pseudophase between the substrate i.e. dye molecules and surfactant molecules resulting in formation of an intermediate which reacts more rapidly with the oxidant. Thus the rate of reaction increases.

Piszkiwicz's model :

The kinetics of micelle catalysis resembles that of enzymatic catalysis in that the micelle may be saturated by the substrate and conversely, the substrate may be saturated by the micelle¹³. Piszkiwicz described an additional similarity of micelle and enzymatic reactions. The rate constants of micelle-catalysed reactions when plotted vs surfactant concentration give sigmoid shaped curves. To describe the dependence of rate constant on [surfactant] a mathematical model based on the reaction mechanism proposed by Bruce *et al.*¹³ is applied. It assumes that a substrate S, and a number n of the surfactant

molecules D, aggregate to form catalytic micelles D_nS, which may then yield the product.

K_D is the dissociation constant of micelle, k_m is the rate of the reaction within the micelle, and k_w is the reaction rate in the absence of the surfactant. The rate expression for this scheme is given as

$$k_\psi = k_m[D]^n + k_w K_D / K_D + [D]_n$$

where, k_m is the rate maximum obtained in the presence of catalyst. This analysis was applied only to the region of detergent concentration wherein the acceleration in reaction rate is observed. On rearranging the above equation we get

$$\log [(k_\psi - k_w)/(k_m - k_\psi)] = n \log [D] - \log K_D$$

Accordingly, a plot of $\log [(k_\psi - k_w)/(k_m - k_\psi)]$ versus $\log [D]$ is linear with a slope 'n' called the index of cooperativity. In the present case the value of n was found to be 1.15. At $\log [(k_\psi - k_w)/(k_m - k_\psi)] = 0$, the value of n $\log [D]$ becomes equal to $\log K_D$ and catalysis by the surfactant shows one half of its maximum effect on rate constant. The value of $\log [D]$ at this point has been designed as $\log [D]_{50}$. The value of K_D and $[D]_{50}$ has been found to be 2.35×10^{-4} and 7.0×10^{-4} respectively. A small K_D value suggests that dissociation of the substrate bound to surfactant is negligible.

Raghavan and Srinivasan's model : Raghavan and Srinivasan¹⁴ developed a model, for bimolecular micelle catalysed reactions, which also predict constancy in K_{obs} values at high detergent concentrations and can be used for evaluating the binding constants of reactions.

According to this model observed rate constants in presence of surfactant is given as,

$$\frac{(k_\psi - k_w)}{k_\psi} \times \frac{1}{[D]^n} = (K_1 K_2) \frac{k_m}{k_\psi} - K_1 \{ 1 + K_2 [S]_T \}$$

and predicts a linear relationship between $[(k_\psi - k_w)/k_\psi] \times 1/[D]^n$ with (k_m/k_ψ) . We have applied this model in our system using the value of n obtained from Piszkiwicz's cooperativity model. The plot of $[(k_\psi -$

Scheme 2

$k_w/k_p] \times 1/[D]^n$ vs $[k_m/k_p]$ was not found to be linear, thus suggesting that both the reactants are not distributed in the micelle phase.

Surfactant catalysed mechanism : Addition of aqueous solution of C₁₆TAB to the solution of acridine orange shows hyperchromic shift. The cause of interaction is electrostatic interaction that overweighs the electronic repulsion. This interactive localisation of the reacting species in the relatively small volume of the micelles compared to the bulk solution leads to a large increase in the effective concentration and as a result the observed rate (in terms of moles per unit time per litre of the entire solution). In the present case as described earlier in the Piszkiwicz model, Menger and Portnoy's model we have seen that there is a substrate promoted micellization and a pseudo phase has also come into being. Since Raghavan and Srinivasan's model has not been found applicable suggesting that both the reactants are not distributed in the pseudo phase, we propose the following C₁₆TAB catalysed reaction mechanism.

The chemistry of remaining reaction scheme is same as for the un-catalysed reaction.

Conclusion :

The plausible mechanisms for the un-catalyzed and C₁₆TAB catalyzed oxidation of acridine orange by acidic chlorite are based on kinetic approach. Acridine orange is a water-soluble, stable dye exhibiting a sharp absorption peak with no shift due to pH changes. Its reaction with acidic chlorite provides insight into scope of chlorite and other halogen compounds as in treatment of toxic

water soluble pollutants and role of auxiliary chemicals like surfactants when present in the textile industrial colour effluents.

References

1. R. Santus, C. Kohen, E. Kohen, J. P. Reyftmann, P. Morliere, L. Dubertret and P. M. Tocci, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1984, **38**, 71.
2. Z. Cizek and V. Studlova, *Talanta*, 1984, **31**, 547.
3. J. H. Fendler and E. J. Fendler, "Catalysis in Micellar and Macro-molecular Systems", Academic Press, New York, 1975.
4. R. C. Elderfield, "Heterocyclic Compounds", 2nd ed., Chapman and Hall, New York, 1957, 6.
5. V. W. Bhagwat, Mona Pipada, S. B. Jonnalagadda and Brijesh Pare, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 1644.
6. Brijesh Pare, V. W. Bhagwat, Rajni Vijay and S. B. Jonnalagadda, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 241.
7. S. B. Jonnalagadda, M. Shezi and N. R. Gollapalli, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2002, **34**, 542.
8. R. G. Kieffer and G. Gordon, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 235; I. Fabian and G. Gordon, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 2144.
9. R. Chinake and R. H. Simoyi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1997, **101**, 1207.
10. I. R. Epstein, K. Kustin and R. H. Simoyi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 5852.
11. F. M. Menger and C. E. Portnoy, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 4698.
12. I. V. Berezin, K. Martinek and A. K. Yatsimirski, *Russ. Chem. Rev.*, 1973, **42**, 787.
13. D. Piszkiwicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1550.
14. P. S. Raghavan and V. S. Srinivasan, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1987, **98**, 199.